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19 July 2024

Dr. Florentinus Pambudi Widiatmaka, ST, MT

Politeknik Ilmu Pelayaran Semarang

Jl. Singosari No.2A, Wonodri, Kec. Semarang Sel.

Kota Semarang, Central Java 50242

Dear Dr. Florentinus, Pambudi Widiatmaka, ST, MT

Research Ethical Approval

Project title: I want to leave as soon as possible, but how can it be Reduced? A Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction and Sanctification

The PIP Semarang Academic and General Affairs Department has approved the above research project:

No .of Animal Ethical Approval : S.Ket PIP.Smg **KP 004 /11/24/PIP46** Tahun 2024

Title: I want to leave as soon as possible, but how can it be Reduced? A Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction and Sanctification

Name of Principal Investigator: Dr. Florentinus Pambudi Widiatmaka, ST, MT
Name of Co-Investigator:

1. Dr. Ali muktar sitompul

This approval is granted based on the submission presented by Iwan Kurniawan, MPd, M.Mar.E as the assigned officer.

Yours sincerely,

Iwan Kurniawan, MPd, M.Mar.E

Head of Academic and General Affairs Department